

SCHOOL HEADS' MANAGEMENT PRACTICES: ITS IMPLICATION TO TEACHER'S INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 9

Pages: 1049-1054

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3026

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14843967

Manuscript Accepted: 10-14-2024

School Heads' Management Practices: Its Implication to Teacher's Instructional Competence

Rubie M. Tuyogon*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The goal of the study was to ascertain how the management styles of school heads affected the instructional competency of their faculty. Results show that school heads extremely performed their management practices while majority of the teachers had an “outstanding” instructional competence or teaching performance. However, teachers' instructional competency is unaffected by the management styles used by school administrators. It was recommended that the school heads have to continuously and competently perform their management functions and intensify its performance in order to inspire more teachers to sustain outstanding performance. Additionally, teachers are encouraged to be resilient in their teaching to sustain outstanding performance and encourage others to improve their instructional competence. Subsequently, it was recommended that an empirical research should be conducted in order to ascertain specific features or teaching characteristics and instructional competence of highly proficient teachers which are useful and can be emulated by proficient teachers.

Keywords: *school heads' management practices, teachers' instructional competence*

Introduction

School heads have the spirited role to play in the academic growth and development of the school organization and better prepare students with the 21st century skills with knowledge, skills, attitudes and values. The capacity of the academic institution to provide quality education through relevant theoretical and educational experiences among learners in a vibrant learning environment with innovative and competitive teachers requires school heads' management effectiveness. The framework of this study is circumscribed on the context of legal and philosophical underpinnings pursuant to section 4 of rule 3 (Duties and Obligations of the School Heads) of the Education Act of 1982 which mandates that “the school head or school principals shall perform their duties to the school by discharging their responsibilities in accordance with the philosophy, goals, and objectives of the school and develop as well as maintain a healthy school atmosphere conducive to harmonious and progressive school-personnel relationships, and to the promotion and preservation of academic freedom and effective teaching-learning, assume and maintain professionalism in the exercise of their leadership in their work and in their dealings with students, teachers, academic non-teaching personnel, administrative staff, and parents or guardians”.

According to Ajao (2018), improving circumstances at the school level is largely dependent on the management strategies used by school heads. It includes every significant factor pertaining to instruction, management, student learning, and community involvement.

Further, it was accentuated that school heads' management practices focuses on teachers' instructional competence which includes classroom management, student-learning attitude participation, and students' performance and achievements in academic and non-academic activities. Additionally, they initiate plan that will spawn the development of schools by having the idea that respectable schools are concomitant with the characteristics of having strong instructional management, rich learning opportunities, and have the features of a encouraging academic and instructional environment.

Management practices of school heads inspire teachers to improve their instructional competence. Laude (2016) espoused that competent teachers can communicate content and ideas to students effectively, adaptable, compassionate, set goals for the entire school, plan their objectives for each lesson on weekly basis and are concerned with teaching and take responsibility for the academic achievements of students.

Further, Magulod (2017) purported that teachers who are competent in their instructional activities will use active learning methods, involving practical activities, problem-solving strategies, reflection and developing critical thinking strategies.

Subsequently, it was emphasized by Sebastian, et al (2017) that teachers' instructional competence includes their communication and interpersonal skills, ability to organize and plan for classroom activities, implement effective classroom management, facilitation and engagement, provides assessment and evaluation to monitor performance, forges collaboration and teamwork, shows caring attitude attitudes towards learners, and flexible and adaptable.

However, there are variables that predict teachers' instructional competence but the researcher is more interested to determine the influence of school heads' management practices to teachers' instructional competence. Hence, this study.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to ascertain the instructional competency of the teachers and the management practices of the school heads at Pedro Maligmat Integrated School in Lunao, Division of Gingoog City, for the 2023–2024 academic year. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the School Head's Management Practices of Pedro Malignat Integrated School?
2. What is the Teachers' Instructional Competence when they are categorized as:
 - 2.1. outstanding;
 - 2.2. very satisfactory;
 - 2.3. satisfactory;
 - 2.4. unsatisfactory; and
 - 2.5. poor?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the Teachers' Instructional Competence and the School Heads' Management Practices ?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design used in the study was descriptive correlational. According to Calderon et al. (2012), descriptive research is an investigation or fact-finding inquiry. It is used to gain a comprehensive understanding of the main reasons of the situations that are presented.

In addition, descriptive design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of adapted survey questionnaires.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the school head and thirty (30) teachers of Pedro Malignat Integrated School, Division of Gingoog City, School Year 2023-2024.

The researcher uses the purposive sampling procedure in choosing the respondents of the study. For the teachers' teaching performance, respondents were evaluated through their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) for the same school year.

Instrument

The study utilized a survey questionnaire adapted from Vicera and Maico (2021) who conducted a study on the impact of school heads' management effectiveness to teachers' instructional competence.

The survey instrument is composed of two (2) major components. The first component is the school heads' management practices with ten (10) indicators, while the second part is the teachers' instructional competence based on the individual performance commitment review (IPCR) evaluation results for the school year 2020-2021.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and School Principal to conduct the study.

After the approval, the researcher administered the survey questionnaire to the respondents and immediately retrieves the said questionnaire. After the respondents provided their responses , researcher summarized and tabulated the data and submitted to the Statistician for the interpretation, analysis, and presentation of the results.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment are utilized in the study;

Problem 1. Mean value and standard deviation were used to present the management practices of school heads.

Problem 2 Range of scores and Percentages were used to present the teachers' instructional competence.

Problem 3. To determine the significant association between teachers' instructional competence and school leaders' management effectiveness, Spearman-Rank Order Correlation, or Spearman-Rho, was employed.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on school heads' management practices its implication to teachers' instructional competence. Based on the issues raised, a survey questionnaire's

responses are analyzed and interpreted to gather data.

Problem 1: What is the extent of school heads' management practices?

Table 1. Mean Distribution of School Heads' Management Practices

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Provides direction, implements programs according to plan.	4.03	.764	Highly Practiced
2. Motivates teachers for continuous professional development.	4.76	.430	Very Highly Practiced
3. Efficiently utilizes school's material resources.	4.00	.000	Highly Practiced
4. Shows positivity and approaches issues and challenges positively.	4.40	.498	Very Highly Practiced
5. Forges strong rapport with teachers and stakeholders.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Practiced
6. Maintains two-way communication in the school organization.	4.60	.498	Highly Practiced
7. Recognizes and praises teachers for extraordinary accomplishments.	4.20	.996	Highly Practiced
8. Challenges teachers to continually improve teaching.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Practiced
9. Encourages teachers to utilize innovative research-based instruction.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Practiced
10. Enthuse teachers to observe quality and make work better.	4.00	.000	Highly Practiced
Overall Mean	4.50	.319	Very Highly Practiced

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very Highly Practiced/3.41-4.20 Highly Practiced/2.62-3.40 Moderately Practiced/1.81-2.60 Seldom Practiced/1.00-1.80 Never Practiced

The mean distribution of management strategies used by school heads is shown in Table 1. With a mean score of 4.50 (SD=.319), the respondents evaluated the school heads' management strategies as "Very Highly Practiced" overall. This finding suggests that school administrators engaged in exceptionally good management and leadership techniques. Based on research, it can be concluded that in order for students to regularly perform well in school and for teaching and learning to take place in the classroom, school leaders must appropriately and closely oversee instructors and students.

The indicators which state that "forges strong rapport with teachers and stakeholders"; "challenges teachers to continually improve in teaching"; and, "encourages teachers to utilize innovative research-based instruction" obtained the highest mean of 5.00 (SD=.000) which is verbally described as "very highly practiced". According to the findings, school administrators have cultivated a strong bond with educators and other stakeholders, and they regularly push instructors to further enhance their teaching skills by attending seminars, conferences, and graduate programs.

Buitizon (2021) avowed that school heads are normally initiate change in the school organization through challenging teachers to be innovative and utilize the research-based instruction in order to make a difference in the lives of their learners. Additionally, school heads necessitate to stimulate forging collaboration between teachers and stakeholders in order to ensure proper implementation of school programs and activities.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.00 (SD=.000) is verbally described as "highly practiced" in the indicators "efficiently utilizes school's material resources" and "enthuse teachers to observe quality and make work better". The results imply that the school heads proficiently used and appropriated school's resources for its purpose and stimulate teachers to always observe quality in their teaching and in their work.

These findings were supported by Llagas (2021) who suggests that school heads performance effectiveness are measured in terms of the implementation of its management and leadership functions such as proper utilization of the school's material and financial resources, teachers' teaching development through quality trainings for the school teaching personnel, and driving teachers to elucidate quality teaching.

Problem 2: What is the teachers' instructional competence when categorized as; Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, and, Poor?

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Teachers' Instructional Competence

Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	16	53.0
Very Satisfactory	14	47.0
Satisfactory	0	.0
Unsatisfactory	0	0
Poor	0	0
Total	30	100.0

Table 2 presents the frequency distribution of teachers' instructional competence. Results indicate that 16 out of 30 or 53% of the teacher-respondents achieved the rating of "outstanding" instructional competence while 14 or 47% achieved "very satisfactory" instructional competence. These findings indicate that teachers performed exceptionally and exceedingly in teaching which means they

excelled in their teaching profession.

It can be deduced based on findings that teachers can effectively carry out their roles and functions in the classroom, constantly innovate, and adapt to the dynamic needs of learners for mastery of the basic competencies of the different learning areas.

Lucero (2020) affirmed that teachers who have the instructional competence enable them to excel academically. They can manifest knowledge, skills, attitudes, motivation, and personal characteristics that enable them to act effectively and proficiently. Additionally, it was also emphasized that effective teachers possessed the skills in instructional management which include strong work ethics, problem-solving abilities, leadership skills, knowledge of the content or subject area and adaptability needed to employ variety of teaching modes and methods.

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between teachers' instructional competence and the school heads' management practices?

Table 3. *Significant Relationship between Teachers' Instructional Competence and School Heads' Management Practices*

Management Practices	Teachers' Instructional Competence			
	(r)	P-Value	Interpretation	Decision on Hol
School Heads' Management Practices	.037	.848	Denotes negligible Correlation	Accepted

**significant at p<0.05 alpha level*

The test of a substantial association between the instructional competency of teachers and the management practices of school heads is presented in Table 3. The r value of .037, which is less than the p-value of .848, indicates that the management practices of school heads indicate a minor correlation to teachers' instructional competency, according to the results. Consequently, the null hypothesis was approved.

This result indicates that school heads' management practices do not influence or affect teachers' instructional competence. This means that even without school heads providing support and stimulating teachers to perform better in their teaching job, still teachers can perform exceedingly outstanding in their teaching performance. It can be deduced based on findings that school heads' management practices are not the predictor variable for teachers' instructional competence but there are other variables other than school heads' management practices that influence teachers' instructional competence or teaching performance.

The results were in contradiction to those of Lucero (2020), who contended that school heads' leadership and management styles have an impact on teachers' work performance and instructional competency. Developing a strong rapport with teachers to encourage them to work proficiently, encouraging them to take advantage of professional development opportunities, and helping school heads implement their programs are all inspiring ways to improve the instructional competency of teachers.

Conclusions

From the findings, it was concluded that in general, that school heads' management practices influence teachers' instructional competence.

The study concluded that the school heads' management practices were extremely implemented and practiced which means they were able to implement the school programs and activities; develop and properly utilized human and material resources in school, and at the same time properly motivate and stimulate teachers and stakeholders to collaborate in school programs and activities.

Further, it also concluded that teachers' commitment to their instructional functions has contributed to their exemplary instructional competence and teaching performance. Teachers who are dedicated and committed to their teaching functions are stimulated to perform exceedingly in teaching and in their non-teaching functions.

Subsequently, it can be resolved further that school heads' management practices do not influence teachers' instructional competence. This implies that school heads' management practices are not the predictive variable for teachers' instructional competence. Hence, there are other variables other than school heads' management practices that influence and predict teachers' instructional competence.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations were being offered to be considered:

School heads are stimulated to continuously and competently perform their management functions and intensify its performance in order to inspire more teachers to sustain higher performance and others to improve instructional competence.

Teachers are encouraged to be resilient in their teaching in order to sustain their outstanding performance and encourage others to improve their instructional competence through advanced professional development programs and activities.

An empirical research or study should be conducted in order to ascertain specific features or teaching characteristics and instructional competence or teaching performance of highly proficient teachers which is useful and can be emulated by proficient teachers.

References

Ajao, A. (2018). Teachers Effectiveness on students' academic performance. *Journal of Education and Practice* 5 (22)

- Ali, N. (2017). Teachers' perceptions of the relationship between principals' instructional leadership, school culture and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Pakistan (Doctoral Dissertation). University of Malaya. *Journal of Educational Management*, 5(3), 41-63.
- Aquino, G. (1985). *Educational Management. Principles, Functions and Concepts*. Manila, Philippines: Rex Book Store, Company.
- Bar-on, H. 2006. *Working with Administrative Competence: Drive to Managerial Performance*. New York: Consulting Psychologist Press.
- Bennet, T. (2013). *Leadership*. New York: Prentice Hall, Inc.
- Blanchard, K., et al. 2005. *Leadership and the One Minute Manager: Increasing Effectiveness Through Situation Leadership*. New York: William Marrow and Co., Inc.
- Bourn, J. 2006. *Management in Central Local Government: Government and Administration Series*. London: Pitman Publishing Limited.
- Bradberry, A. 2005. *Administrative Performance at work*. New York: Prentice Hall International, Inc.
- Buitizon, S. (2021). Management Practices of School Heads, Organizational Behavior, and Performance of Teachers in Distance Learning Environment. *International Journal of Management, Entrepreneurship, Social Science, and Humanities*, Volume 4 (2), 204-228.
- Caruso, D. 2002. *The Management Competence Quick Book*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall International, Inc.
- Davis, K. 2004. *Human Behavior at Work: Organizational Behavior*. USA: 6th Ed. McGraw Hill International Book.
- Dramayo, A. (2014). "Administrative Performance of Local Chief Executives of the Province of Surigao Del Sur". Unpublished Master's Thesis, Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Philippines.
- Drucker, P. 1979. *The Effective Executive*. New York: Harper and Row Publishers, Inc.
- Drucker, P. 2005. *Task, Responsibilities, and Practices*. New York: Harper and Row Publishers, Inc.
- Espinas, D. 2009. "A Causal Model of Negotiation Competency of School Administrators in Bukidnon, Philippines". A Dissertation, Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Faiman, F. 2006. *Group Leadership and Democracy*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Co.
- Fraenkel, J. et al. 1993. *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education*. USA: McGraw-Hill, Inc.
- Fulmer, E. et al. (2015). *Exploring New Management*. 3rd Edition. A Study Guide with cases, Readings, Incidents, and Exercises. New Jersey: McMillan Publishing Co. Inc.
- Furnham, A. 2002. *Administrative Performance Assessment*. University College London: UCL Press.
- Gahum, E. (2010). "Instructional Leadership Effectiveness of School Administrators of the Seventh-Day Adventists Colleges in Mindanao". Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Administration. Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Bukidnon. Philippines.
- Goleman, D. 2005. *Administrative Performance: Why It can Matter More Than I.Q.* London: Oxford University Press.
- Goleman, D. 2006. *Administrative Performance: Why It can Matter More Than I.Q. (Second International Edition)*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Gonzales, R. 2014. "Management Practices of Bukidnon Secondary Schools Administrators". Unpublished Master's Thesis, Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Greaves, S. 2005. *Multi-Rater Assessment and Self-Management Assessment*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Hallinger, P, & Bryant, D. A. (2013). Review of research publication on educational leadership and management in Asia: A comparative analysis of three regions. *Oxford Review of Education*, 39 (3), 307-328.
- Herrera, R. (2010). *Principal leadership and school effectiveness. Perspectives from principals and teachers*. <http://scholarworks.wmich.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1570content=dissertations>.
- Holt, D. 2007. *Management Principles and Practices*. Eaglewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall, Inc.
- House, R. 1991. *Management Theory*. The Wharton School. University of Pennsylvania. Philadelphia: University Press.
- House, R.J. (1971). A path-goal theory of leader effectiveness. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 16, 32-338.

- Jafee, J., et al. 2005. *The Art of Managing: How to Access and Perfect Your Management Style*. Massachusetts: Adison-Wesley Publishing Co. Inc.
- Khan, A. (2013). A case study of instructional contributions of community and government secondary school administrators in Pakistan. *Journal of Education and Vocational Research*, 4 (2), 47-59.
- Koontz, H., et al. (2004). *Principles of Management: An Analysis of Managerial Functions*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Landy, L. 2005. *Trait-based Administrative Competence Self-Efficacy*. New York: Cornell University Press.
- Llagas, C. (2021). *Becoming 21st Century Educational Leaders*. *Journal for Management and Leadership*. Volume 2(2).
- Lucero, J. (2020). *Instructional Competence of Teachers: Basis for Learning Action Cell*. *International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning*. Vol. 5, issue 4.
- Magulod, G. (2017). *Factors of school effectiveness and performance of selected public and private elementary schools: implications on educational planning in the Philippines*. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, Vol. 5, No. 1.
- Martires, M. 2005. *Introduction to Management*. Massachusetts: Adison-Wesley Publishing Co. Inc.
- Mayer, C. 2001. *Organizational Performance Effectiveness*. Boston, Massachusetts: Kent Publishing Company. A Division of Wodsworth, Inc.
- McAlpine, T. 2004. *The Process of Management: Major Features of Management Performance*. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House, Pvt. Ltd.
- Mukhi, S. (2014). "Relationship Between Leadership Styles, Climate and Performance of the Organization". *Dissertation Abstract International*, University of New South Wales, Australia.
- Namoc, E. 2006. "Administrative Organizational Performance of Department Heads of Service Units of the Provincial Government of Bukidnon". Unpublished Master's Thesis. Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Niggro, N., et al. (1989). *Introduction to Public Administration*. USA: McGraw-Hill Publishing Company, Inc.
- Paulhus, D., et al. 2006. *Meta-analyses of Administrative Competence*. International Edition. New York: Consulting Psychologist Press.
- Payne, S. 2006. *Administrative Performance Book*. International Publication. USA: McGraw Hill Book, Co.
- Petrides, K. 2002. *Administrative and Organizational Performance Global Assessment Test*. London: University of London Press.
- Plunkett, A. 2005. *Introduction to Management*. 5th edition, Boston, Massachusetts: Kent Publishing Company. A Division of Woods worth, Inc.
- Reid, S., et al. 2006. *Global Administrative Performance Assessment and Appraisal*. International Edition. USA: McGraw Hill Book, Co.
- Reuven, B. 2006. *Administrative Performance Inventory*. New York: Consulting Psychologist Press.
- Salovey, P. 2002. *A Study on Administrative Performance: Developing Administrative Competence*. International Edition. USA: McGraw Hill Book, Co.
- Stoner, J., et al. 2007. *Management*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall International Editions, 5th Edition.
- Stydell, R. (2013). *Fundamental of Management*. 6th edition, USA: McGraw Hill Publishing Company, Inc.
- Ullman, A. 1996. *Developing model parameters in linear relationships of variables*. 2nd edition, USA: McGraw Hill Publishing Company, Inc.
- Vicera, C., Maico, E. (2021). *Impact of school heads management styles on the teacher's instructional competence and school performance*. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research*.
- Waltman, A. 2014. *Human Resource Management*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall International Edition. 3rd Edition.
- Wankel, D. 2003. *Organizational Communication*. 3rd edition, Kent Publishing Company. New York: McGraw Hill Book Co.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Rubie M. Tuyogon

St. Peter's College – Philippines